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D2.4 – Development of a framework for the combination of HPC and HPDA operations

*WP2: Convergence of HPC/HPDA and Improved
Usability*

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the different approaches of the BioExcel CoE regarding the design and development of a framework for the combination of High Performance Computing (HPC) and High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) operations, and the initial workflows that will benefit from such a framework. The BioExcel HPC-HPDA framework combines two state-of-the-art techniques: Machine Learning (ML) algorithms to automatically learn from generated data, and *Big Data* approaches to store, combine, analyse, and retrieve large amounts of information.

Focusing on the ML field, a new category for the BioExcel Building Blocks (BioBB) library has been implemented: `biobb_ml`. This module contains a set of building blocks wrapping popular ML libraries such as Scikit-learn and TensorFlow. The collection of building blocks contained in the `biobb_ml` module is divided in six categories that are presented in section 2 of this document: Classification, Regression, Clustering, Neural Networks, Dimensionality Reduction and Utils. The module offers an easy way of training, testing and prediction with common ML methods like Random Forest, K-Means or Neural Networks. Including these building blocks in the BioBB library expands the collection of tools wrapped and allows generating complex reproducible workflows including ML models.

In parallel with the `biobb_ml` module, a new ML library, offering large-scale data analytics on HPC infrastructures, has been developed: `dislib`. Based on distributed arrays (`ds-arrays`), `dislib` divides the input data in blocks that are processed in parallel, eventually performing a reduction to yield the results (`map/reduce`), reducing the execution time while at the same time supporting larger input data sets. Thanks to the BioExcel contribution, the library has been extended with a couple of widely used methods in the computational biomolecular simulation field: Principal Component Analysis and Daura's clustering. The library is now able to read different MD trajectory formats as input. Preliminary tests presented in section 3 are showing encouraging results, with the possibility to apply these methods to extremely large trajectory files. `dislib` functionalities will be integrated in the `biobb_ml` module in new releases.

Workflows using ML methods for large-scale scientific projects are presented to showcase how these technologies are applied in our field. Two very different endeavors, one focused on predicting Protein-DNA binding affinities in transcription factors, and one predicting RNA interaction energies reproducing Quantum Mechanics (QM) results, are briefly presented in section 4.

Finally, an HPDA *Big Data* approach, with a NoSQL database storing trajectories of COVID-19 related simulations is described in section 5. The database and its connected server provide an interactive and graphical interface to quickly browse key structural and flexibility features of the most important proteins involved in SARS-CoV-2 host invasion. The server is an example of a large collaborative effort, and showcases the importance of *Big Data* and data analytics in the biomolecular simulation field.

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1 Introduction

The combination of High Performance Computing (HPC) and High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) allows the generation and subsequent efficient processing of intricate *Big Data* analyses. Combining them, one can quickly generate and examine large data sets and draw conclusions about the information they contain. Two approaches resulted particularly promising using the HPC-HPDA combination: generating large amounts of data and 1) using Machine Learning (ML) algorithms to process and automatically learn from this data; and 2) using *Big Data* approaches to store, combine, analyse, and finally efficiently retrieve this newly generated information.

ML is a branch of artificial intelligence (AI) where systems can learn from data, identifying patterns and making decisions with minimal human intervention. It has become one of the most popular and widely used computational tools over the last decade. Indeed, a ML study has produced the most recent breakthrough in the field, solving a 50-year-old grand challenge in biology: the possibility to predict protein structures from their residue sequence ([DeepMind's AlphaFold 2](#)). The increased computational power and the appearance of new Graphical Processor Units (GPUs), together with the capacity of generating and collecting an unprecedented amount of data, have led to an exponential growth of these techniques, especially in industry and business while in the scientific fields it has reached wide adoption; bioinformaticians have applied ML especially for predicting pathological mutation [1]. In computational biomolecular simulations, this integration has been slower, but has boomed over the last five years [2, 3] taking advantage of the large amounts of data that biomolecular simulations produce to train machine-learning algorithms. Other ML methods (e.g. Neural Networks, Random Forests, dimensionality reduction methods) are already used in analysing trajectories, accelerating biomolecular simulations, and parameterizing force fields thus making biomolecular simulations an ideal field for the adoption of ML techniques.

Big Data is a term used to describe large amounts of data that can be mined for information. The term became popular among data managers in the year 2000, when generating large *volumes* of *varied* data at high *velocity* (what is known as the 3 Vs) became feasible. Computational biomolecular simulations can be considered nowadays a *Big Data* field. TeraBytes (TB) of data are regularly generated in a single Molecular Dynamics (MD) project using HPC supercomputers. If we store different trajectories for a particular protein family from various research projects in a single database, the amount of data can easily reach the PetaByte (PB) regime (e.g. GPCRmd [4] or BioExcel-CV19). A direct consequence of the *Big Data* era was the appearance of the so-called NoSQL systems. These systems changed the modality of data storage, which was dominated at that time by SQL databases. NoSQL databases were designed to deal with the limitations of SQL (relational) databases: scaling, replication, and performance. NoSQL systems are typically distributed data repositories allowing for easy horizontal scaling, dividing the system dataset, and loading over multiple servers. Due to their distributed architecture, these systems provide better efficiency than a single server database, and are capable of handling huge

amounts of data and/or very high frequencies of read/write requests, especially when the queries can be parallelized and scattered along the different nodes [5]. These NoSQL technologies have been already explored for the MD trajectories by the community, with encouraging results both in terms of efficient storage/retrieval and global analysis, performed in parallel on many trajectories (e.g. a particular molecular fragment present in different trajectories) [6].

Undoubtedly, the field of computational biomolecular simulations is moving towards state-of-the-art approaches such as artificial intelligence and *Big Data* mining. This trend will increase even more in the coming years, with HPC playing a crucial role in the generation of such data. BioExcel CoE's' expertise with HPC infrastructures, simulation codes, and scientific use cases is already aligning its activities to incorporate and pull these techniques together for larger benefit. Examples of this alignment are presented in this document.

2 BioExcel Building Blocks - Machine Learning Module

ML methods have recently become part of the biomolecular simulations. Thus, ML tools should be included in BioExcel's list of routine tools and the biomolecular simulation community we are supporting. We have worked towards this aim by including a new ML module in the BioExcel Building Blocks library. We have deposited the module in the [BioExcel GitHub repository](#), where its six main sections can be found: Classification, Regression, Clustering, Neural Networks, Dimensionality Reduction and Utils. We provide a full list of available ML building blocks and the tools being wrapped in the following section, and short descriptions can be found in the Appendix.

2.1 Classification

Classification analysis is a supervised learning approach used to predict a categorical (discrete) outcome variable based on the value of one or multiple predictor variables: The data is labeled according to some parameters and then the labels are predicted for the data. A typical example is classifying e-mails into spam / not spam. An example application for the biomolecular field is the classification of a particular protein mutation into pathological / non pathological [7].

For the **classification**, we have devised the following building blocks:

- **Classification Predict:** The [ClassificationPredict](#) building block uses a trained model from one of the available classification techniques (see following building blocks) to predict a particular classification from an input data set.
- **Decision Tree:** A decision support tool that uses a tree-like model of decisions and their possible consequences. It can be understood as an algorithm that only contains conditional control statements. The [DecisionTree](#) building block trains and tests a given dataset using the Decision Tree method.
- **K-Nearest Neighbors:** Classification algorithm that assumes that similar things exist in close proximity. The method works by finding the distances between a query and all the features in the data, selecting the specified number of features (K) closest to the query, and then votes for the most frequent label. Choosing the right value for K is crucial for this method. Typically this requires running the algorithm several times with different values of K and choosing the K that reduces the number of errors we do encounter (while maintaining the algorithm's ability to accurately make the right predictions). In order to tackle this issue, two building blocks were implemented in the BioBB library: the [KNeighborsCoefficient](#), which is able to retrieve the best K coefficient for a given dataset, and the [KNeighborsTrain](#), which trains and tests a given dataset using the K-Nearest Neighbors method.

- **Random Forest Classifier:** A method that builds a set of decision trees at training time and gives as a final output the class corresponding to the mode of the classes (most commonly occurring class) of the individual trees forming the forest. [RandomForestClassifier](#) building block trains and tests a given dataset using the Random Forest Classifier method.
- **Support Vector Machine (SVM):** An algorithm that classifies data points by separating them through a high-dimensional plane. SVMs are sometimes also used as regression models. The [SupportVectorMachine](#) building block trains and tests a given dataset using the Support Vector Machine method.
- **Logistic Regression:** A classification algorithm for assigning observations to a discrete set of classes using the logistic sigmoid function to return a probability value that can then be mapped to two or more discrete classes. The [LogisticRegression](#) building block trains and tests a given dataset using the Logistic Regression method.

2.2 Regression

Regression analysis is a supervised learning approach used to predict a continuous outcome variable (y) based on the value of one (x) or multiple (X) predictor variables. The goal of regression models is to build a mathematical equation that defines y as a function of the x or X variable(s). The typical example of ML regression is the prediction of each person's income from his/her age, education, and place of residence. An example application for the biomolecular field is the prediction of binding affinity from ML scoring functions [8].

The building blocks generated for the **regression** methods are:

- **RegressionPredict:** The [RegressionPredict](#) building block uses a trained model from one of the available regression techniques (see following building blocks) to predict a particular regression from an input data set.
- **Linear Regression:** An algorithm taken directly from the statistics field where a dependent variable value (y) is predicted based on a given independent variable (x). The technique finds a linear relationship between x (input) and y (output). The [LinearRegression](#) building block trains and tests a given dataset using the Linear Regression method.
- **Polynomial Regression:** A technique to obtain predictions over supervised data in which a quadratic, cubic or a higher (polynomial) order relation exists. The [PolynomialRegression](#) building block trains and tests a given dataset using the Polynomial Regression method.
- **Random Forest Regression:** A method that builds a set of decision trees at training time and gives the mean/average prediction of the individual trees forming the forest as the output. The [RandomForestRegressor](#)

building block trains and tests a given dataset using the Random Forest Regressor method.

2.3 Clustering

Clustering is an unsupervised learning approach that works partitioning the dataset into groups, called clusters. The goal is to split the data in such a way that points within a single cluster are similar and points from different clusters are different. The typical example of ML clustering is the creation of marketing personas, used to define customer segments with similar profiles and needs. An example application for the biomolecular field is the finding of conformational ensembles from a MD trajectory [9].

The building blocks generated for the **clustering** methods are:

- **ClusteringPredict:** The [ClusteringPredict](#) building block uses a trained model from one of the available clustering techniques (see following building blocks) to perform a particular clustering to an input data set.
- **Agglomerative Clustering:** It is the most common type of hierarchical clustering used to group objects by clusters based on their similarity. Similarly to the previously described K-Nearest Neighbors approach, determining where to cut the hierarchical tree into clusters is crucial, thus two different building blocks were implemented in the BioBB library: the [AgglomerativeCoefficient](#), which is able to find the best cutoff threshold for a given dataset, and the [AgglClustering](#), which trains and tests a given dataset using the Agglomerative Clustering method.
- **DBScan (Density-Based Spatial clustering of applications with noise):** It is one of the most common density-based clustering algorithms. Points that are closely packed together in high-density regions (i.e. points with many nearby neighbors) are grouped, marking as outliers points which are isolated in low-density regions (i.e. whose nearest neighbors are too far away). The [DBSCANClustering](#) building block trains and tests a given dataset using the DBScan method.
- **K-Means:** It is one of the most popular clustering algorithms. It selects K centroids that are used to define the final clusters, where a point is considered to be in a particular cluster if it is closer to that cluster's centroid than to any other centroid. Similarly to the previously described K-Nearest Neighbors, two building blocks were implemented in the BioBB library: the [KMeansCoefficient](#), which is able to find the best K coefficient for a given dataset, and the [KMeansClustering](#), which trains and tests a given dataset using the K-Means clustering method.
- **Spectral clustering:** It is a clustering technique based on graph theory, which reduces complex multidimensional datasets into clusters of similar data. Again, two building blocks were implemented in the BioBB library:

the [SpectralCoefficient](#), which is able to find the best coefficient for a given dataset, and the [SpecClustering](#), which trains and tests a given dataset using the Spectral clustering method.

2.4 Neural Networks (NN)

Neural networks are a class of ML algorithms used to model complex patterns in datasets, inspired by the way neurons function together to process sensory inputs. NNs learn from processing many labeled examples that are supplied during training: based on this crucial phase, they learn then which input characteristics are needed to construct the correct output. Once a sufficient number of examples have been processed, the neural network can begin to process new, unseen inputs and successfully return accurate results. The more examples and variety of inputs the program sees, the more accurate the results typically become because the program learns with experience. The typical example of ML NN is image recognition, where NNs learn to identify images containing a particular entity (e.g. an animal) by analyzing example images that have been manually categorized (labeled) as representing a given animal. An example application for the biomolecular field is the prediction of QM energies [10].

Neural networks are the backbone of deep learning algorithms. The number of node layers, or depth, which in deep learning is greater than three, is what distinguishes a single neural network from a deep learning algorithm.

The building blocks generated for the **Neural Network** methods are:

- **PredictNeuralNetwork:** The [PredictNeuralNetwork](#) building block uses a trained model from one of the available Neural Network techniques (see following building blocks) to predict complex patterns from an input data set.
- **Classification NN:** It is a type of Neural Network used to tackle a classification problem. The [ClassificationNeuralNetwork](#) building block trains and tests a given dataset using the Classification NN method.
- **Regression NN:** It is a type of Neural Network used to tackle a regression problem. The [RegressionNeuralNetwork](#) building block trains and tests a given dataset using the Regression NN method.
- **Autoencoder NN:** It is a type of Neural Network that generates a representation (encoding) for a dataset, reducing the original dimensionality by training the network to ignore signal noise and to remove redundancies. Typically the reduced encoding is then used to reconstruct the original dataset, in a similar way as a lossy (i.e. irreversible) compression does. The [AutoencoderNeuralNetwork](#) building block trains and tests a given dataset using the Autoencoder NN method.

- **Decoding NN:** The [DecodingNeuralNetwork](#) building block decodes a dataset from the model file trained with the Autoencoder NN method.
- **Recurrent NN:** It is a type of Neural Network designed to process inputs of variable length, with the ability to retain information about what has been calculated so far (i.e. memory). This type of Neural Network is called recurrent because it performs the same task for every element of the input sequence, with the output being dependent on the previous computations. The [RecurrentNeuralNetwork](#) building block trains and tests a given dataset using the Recurrent NN method.

2.5 Dimensionality Reduction

Dimensionality reduction in ML is the transformation of data from a high-dimensional space into a low-dimensional space so that the low-dimensional representation retains some meaningful properties of the original data. These techniques are typically used in applied ML to simplify a classification or regression dataset in order to better fit a predictive model, as more input features often make a predictive modeling task more challenging to model (i.e. overfitting), and can also affect the training performance. The typical example of Dimensionality Reduction is to obtain data patterns from large amounts of data obtained from signal processing (e.g. astronomy). An example application for the biomolecular field is the finding of the essential dynamic movements of a molecule from a MD trajectory [11].

The building blocks generated for the **dimensionality reduction** methods are:

- **Principal Component Analysis (PCA):** It is a popular statistical method to reduce the dimensionality of a dataset. PCA identifies a list of principal axes to describe the underlying dataset (i.e. principal components, eigenvectors) and then ranks them according to the amount of variance captured by each (eigenvalues). PCA is broadly used for reducing, compressing, and visualizing global movements present in MD trajectories [11]. The [PrincipalComponentAnalysis](#) building block reduces the dimensionality of a given dataset using the PCA method.
- **Partial Least Squares (PLS):** It is a dimensionality reduction method based on projections where highly multivariate data is projected into a smaller coordinate space (latent variables). The [PLSComponents](#) building block computes the best number of components for a particular input dataset, whereas the [PLS Regression](#) building block reduces the dimensionality of a given dataset using the PLS method.

2.6 Utils

This section describes a set of building blocks developed as transversally useful utilities convenient for many different ML methods. Generating plots from the resulting models or reformatting the values of the input datasets are just examples of blocks included in this category. The list of utils building blocks will be expanded with the number of ML methods included in the `biobb_ml` module.

- **Plots:** Results from ML methods are often represented using graphical illustrations (e.g. feature correlations, cluster divisions). Building blocks generating characteristic plots in the ML field are developed and included in the `biobb_ml` category.
 - The [Correlation Matrix](#) building block computes a correlation matrix from a given dataset and generates a correlation heatmap.
 - The [Dendrogram](#) building block that plots an input matrix dataset as a hierarchically-clustered dendrogram.
 - The [Pairwise Comparison](#) building block plots multiple pairwise bivariate distributions in a given input dataset, representing the relationship for $(n = 2)$ combinations of the input variables as a matrix of plots where the diagonal plots are univariate histogram plots.
- **Dataset reformation:** The input dataset used for training usually has to be modified to adapt it to the particular method. These modifications are commonly required in many different methods and have been converted to building blocks of the BioBB library for convenience.
 - The [Dummy Variables](#) building block converts a categorical variable into a dummy/indicator variable (i.e. numeric variable).
 - The [Map Variables](#) building block maps the values of an input series according to input correspondence, substituting each value in a series with another value, which may be derived from a function, a dictionary, or another series.

3 Dislib - Machine Learning Distributed Computing Library

3.1 Dislib Library

The combination of HPC and HPDA implies the processing of large amounts of data. An efficient way to process this data is using distribution across computational nodes, a method adopted by various solutions, including recent databases. *Dislib* [12] is a distributed ML library that enables large-scale data analytics on HPC infrastructures. Its interface is inspired by scikit-learn [13], providing an estimator-based interface that improves productivity by making models easy to use and interchangeable. This interface also makes programming with dislib easy for scientists who are already familiar with scikit-learn. Dislib also provides a distributed data structure (ds-array) that can be operated as a regular Python object. The combination of this data structure and the estimator-based interface makes dislib a distributed-computing version of scikit-learn, where communications, data transfers, and parallelism are automatically handled behind the scene.

Dislib is built on top of PyCOMPSs [14], a task-based programming model and runtime that is well suited for scientific applications and applications that process large amounts of data. PyCOMPSs offers good scalability and performance in distributed infrastructures, including clusters, clouds, supercomputers, and Docker-managed systems. Since PyCOMPSs automatically manages the infrastructure and the distribution of the computation, dislib applications can run in multiple platforms without changing the source code, and without having to worry about platform-specific details, such as IP addresses and storage devices. In addition, dislib applications can also include custom PyCOMPSs tasks to perform data pre-processing or post-processing in parallel or to combine computational workloads with data analytics.

Dislib exposes the different ML algorithms of the library through an estimator-based interface. An estimator is anything that learns from data. The typical workflow when working with dislib consists of the following steps: 1) load data into a ds-array, 2) instantiate an estimator with parameters, 3) fit the estimator with the ds-array, and 4) make predictions on new data or extract information from the estimator.

Distributed arrays (ds-arrays) is the main data structure used in dislib. In essence, a ds-array is a matrix divided in blocks that are stored remotely. Each block of a ds-array is a [NumPy](#) array or a SciPy [CSR matrix](#), depending on the type of data used to create the ds-array. Dislib provides an API similar to NumPy to work with ds-arrays in a completely sequential way. However, ds-arrays are not stored in the local memory. This means that ds-arrays can store much more data than regular NumPy arrays. When comparing the performance of dislib, not only is it able to reduce the execution time but also support larger input data sets (compared to MLLib and Dask-ML).

The two main methods used in the dislib models are fit (ds-array) and predict (ds-array). The *fit* method computes estimator statistics using the input

data. The *predict* method typically computes the labels of unlabeled samples given a fitted estimator. Both *fit* and *predict* methods are internally parallelized with PyCOMPSs. In most cases, this means that dislib processes each block of the ds-array in parallel, and eventually performs some kind of reduction to get the final results, or to decide whether the algorithm has converged.

Dislib is available as open source and currently has methods for data management, classification, clustering, regression, decomposition, and model selection.

3.2 Implementation of Daura's clustering algorithm

Clustering is one of the unsupervised learning techniques that provides a way to separate the elements from a given set of data into distinct groups, where given characteristics within each group are typically more similar than those outside the group. There are multiple clustering algorithms, and dislib already provides implementations for several of them, more specifically: DBSCAN, K-means, and Gaussian mixtures [15].

In this section we focus on the clustering algorithm defined by Daura et al. [11]. Modern MD simulations generate large datasets containing hundreds of gigabytes or more of trajectory data tracking the positions of a system's atoms over time. Daura's algorithm is needed to meaningfully separate protein structures from a trajectory, so that each group of structures exhibits unique properties from the rest.

The algorithm also gives an idea of the center of each group, since the center is close to the average, i.e. the protein structure, which is the most descriptive of that group. While in theory the center can be a real structure that exists in the trajectory or rather a fictitious average, Daura's algorithm returns as center an existing structure. The algorithm is implemented in almost all molecular dynamics analysis packages, such as VMD [16] or GROMACS [17].

The algorithm has been parallelized with PyCOMPSs and integrated in dislib. It has been implemented with an initial phase with a significant amount of parallelism, with tasks that explore the number of structures within the distance cutoff for each possible center. Later, an iterative algorithm searches the largest cluster in each iteration, where parallelization is only possible within each iteration. Each iteration also includes a synchronization point to obtain the cluster, followed by a smaller parallel part where the structure set is updated by removing the structures included in the last cluster.

Besides Daura's clustering algorithm, we have also implemented a PyCOMPSs script that computes the RMSD matrix as a ds-array.

The algorithm was tested in MareNostrum supercomputer, using a large trajectory file (100,001 frames and 31,632 atoms). The new dislib implementation completed the clustering, using 32 nodes of MN4, in 3 hours and

30 minutes (Fig. 3.1). The maximum memory usage in this case is of 32 x 48 Gigabyte, which corresponds to 1.5 Terabytes. The memory occupancy is approximately of about 87% in all nodes, as can be seen in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Memory usage during the execution of the Daura's clustering with dislib and a trajectory file containing 100,001 frames and 31,632 atoms. The execution was done in 32 nodes of MareNostrum4 and took 3 hours and 30 minutes. The maximum memory usage was of 32 x 48 Gigabytes, corresponding to 1.5 Terabytes

3.3 PCA with Singular Value Decomposition

When trying to use an earlier version of the dislib PCA with large trajectories, we identified an important limitation of this previous implementation. The algorithm computed the covariance matrix of the input and then the eigen decomposition of this covariance matrix using NumPy. The computation of the covariance matrix was performed in parallel; however, its eigen decomposition was done in a single sequential task. This issue was limiting the scalability of PCA, and made the algorithm unfeasible for data sets with a large number of features (since the covariance matrix of an $N \times M$ ds-array is of size $M \times M$), i.e. for trajectories with a large number of atoms. More precisely, an input trajectory of 60,000 snapshots and 6,912 atoms was raising memory errors in MareNostrum 4. Figure 3.2 presents an execution trace of the existing PCA implementation. In this trace, we can observe how the eigen decomposition of the covariance matrix dominates the execution time and limits its scalability.

Figure 3.2: Trace from a PCA execution that shows the limitation in scalability caused by performing the eigen decomposition in a single task. The long green line indicates the time needed by this particular task, clearly higher than the rest of the tasks

During this BioExcel reporting period, we have implemented an alternative way to compute PCA using singular value decomposition (SVD). This new approach improves the scalability of PCA calculation and allows its computation even when the input ds-array has a large number of features.

There are several ways in which eigen decomposition can be parallelized. A common approach is called ‘divide-and-conquer’. In this method, the input matrix is first tri-diagonalized, and then eigen decomposition is solved for two sub-matrices of the input matrix. This tridiagonalization can be repeated for the sub-matrices as well, until their size is sufficiently small and can be decomposed using a sequential method. Finally, the decompositions of the sub-matrices are combined to obtain the eigen decomposition of the original matrix.

Initially, we experimented with an implementation of the divide-and-conquer method, using Householder reflections [18] for the tridiagonalization of the covariance matrix. This tridiagonalization method was providing parallelism, but generated various tasks for each column in the input matrix. This resulted in a large number of small tasks, which is inefficient in distributed environments.

The limitations of parallel eigen decomposition algorithms in distributed platforms led us to SVD. SVD is a factorization of an $N \times M$ matrix into an $N \times N$ unitary matrix called U , an $N \times M$ diagonal matrix Σ , and an $M \times M$ unitary matrix called V . SVD can be used as an alternative method to solve PCA that is applied directly to the input matrix. To solve PCA with SVD there is no need to compute the covariance matrix. SVD for PCA is mathematically equivalent to decomposing the covariance matrix and produces the same results. The advantage of SVD over eigen decomposition is that there are block algorithms for SVD that operate on chunks of the input matrix. This avoids the limitations of eigen decomposition methods in distributed environments as it allows the generation of tasks with higher granularity.

For the computation of SVD in parallel, we have implemented a Block-Jacobi algorithm [19]. The algorithm works by transforming the input matrix (ds-array) iteratively until convergence. In every iteration, the algorithm goes through all pairs of block columns of the input matrix. Then, the algorithm computes a block matrix for each pair of column blocks, factorizes the block matrix, and finally multiplies the result of this factorization with the original matrix. This multiplication eliminates non-diagonal entries in the selected column blocks of the input matrix. After reaching convergence, the algorithm uses the transformed matrix to compute Σ and the unitary matrix U . The computation of the unitary matrix V follows a similar approach, but applies the transformations to an identity matrix.

The way in which the pairs of column blocks are chosen in every iteration of the algorithm has a direct impact on the amount of parallelism. The current implementation of the algorithm follows the simpler approach. This could be improved in the future. Also, the size of the column blocks provides a trade-off between the amount of parallelism and performance. This is because small column blocks generate tasks with low granularity, which can be inefficient in distributed environments.

The computation of PCA with SVD consists of computing the SVD factorization and then applying a simple transformation on Σ . We have integrated the SVD method of PCA in a way that maintains the eigen decomposition method as well. To choose which method to employ, users can pass the *method* argument to the PCA constructor as shown below:

```
pca = PCA(method='svd')  
pca = PCA(method='eig')
```

Figure 3.3 shows an execution trace of PCA with SVD using the input matrix that cannot be computed with the eigen decomposition method. Although the amount of parallelism is limited, we are able to compute the decomposition successfully in 3 hours using a single MareNostrum 4 node.

Figure 3.3: Execution trace of PCA with SVD for an input trajectory of 60,000 snapshots and 6,912 atoms

Figure 3.4 shows the execution times of PCA with SVD for two different trajectory files. The trajectory file with 6,912 atoms represents an input matrix of 60,000 rows and 20,736 columns, whereas the trajectory file with 629 atoms represents an input matrix of 1 million rows and 1,887 columns. We used blocks of size 1,000x500 in the case of 6,912 atoms and 100,000x100 in the case of 629 atoms.

Figure 3.4: Execution times of PCA with SVD for two datasets with a different number of atoms

We see that PCA has limited scalability in both cases. This is because there are not enough concurrent tasks to exploit all the available resources. The number of concurrent tasks in SVD can be increased by reducing the block size. However, this comes at the cost of increased scheduling overhead. We also see that the number of rows and the size of row blocks do not have an impact in SVD's scalability. This confirms that PCA with SVD is well suited for datasets with a large number of columns rather than a large number of rows. The main advantage of PCA with SVD over the covariance method is capable of computing PCA on datasets with a large number of columns.

4 Machine Learning Workflows

ML methods are getting more popular every day in our field. A large number of very different scientific projects are using ML in biomolecular simulations studies, as demonstrated by this special issue of the *Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences* journal [3]. BioExcel's partners are also exploring these methodologies for their projects, and this allows us to integrate our expertise in generating reproducible workflows including ML models for creating predictors that tackle scientific problems. Two representative examples are briefly presented in the following section.

4.1 Protein-DNA Binding Sites Predictor

Essential biological processes such as DNA replication, transcription, splicing, and repair are driven by protein-DNA interactions [20]. Protein residues in the DNA-binding site enclose crucial information for the binding mechanism and DNA-sequence preferences are crucial for forming the DNA-complex and performing the biological activity [21]. The identification of these DNA preferences has been a popular field of study in the last decade. Different types of protein-DNA binding site predictors exist, mainly based on sequence and/or structural data. Our approximation, taking advantage of the HPC resources and pre-exascale MD workflows, is to train a new predictor using a different type of descriptors, DNA conformational and flexibility observables.

The custom ML workflow aims to predict protein-DNA binding affinity based on experimental binding data [22] and computationally derived DNA flexibility features [23].

The input data depends on the experimental technique that has been used to detect protein-DNA sequence selection. We aim at training a ML method able to predict the possible protein-binding affinities taking just a genomic sequence (and protein family) as input.

The input of the training process is a set of DNA 35-mer sequences with their corresponding protein-binding affinities obtained with the Protein Binding Microarrays (PBM) technique [24]. The features used for training the ML are conformational and flexibility properties computed from a set of MD simulations of DNA duplexes covering the 136 existing tetra-nucleotides [23]. From these simulations, helical parameters are extracted using Curves+ program [25]. Average values and stiffness constants for each base pair in a tetramer (Average and Diagonal) and their combinations are then extracted.

To relate the structural and flexibility parameters taken from MD simulations with the 35-mers from the PBM experiments, these long input sequences are split in tetramers, and average and diagonal values are associated to all tetramers, using a sliding window routine. In particular, the most important descriptors for training are the ones describing the rotational and translational movements of DNA base pair steps (Fig. 4.1).

Figure 4.1: Translational (Rise, Slide, Shift) and Rotational (Twist, Roll, Tilt) DNA base-pair step parameters [Image taken from <http://cosweb1.fau.edu/~iyildirim/DNAbending.html>]

The steps presented so far are the central parts of the workflow, with which we could already start training the predictor. On top of them, though, different techniques are applied to improve the prediction rate. For example, the input experimental sequences are shortened. As 35-mers are too long to be recognized as a protein-binding site, they can be shortened to use sequences that better mimic real binding sites. One approximation is to extract an n -mer consensus sequence (with n being smaller than 35) from the top-ranked sequences according to their experimental protein-binding affinity. The consensus sequence and the position-specific probability matrix (PSPM) are extracted using the MEME-suite software [26]. Shorter sequences contained within the 35-mer experimental sequences being equal or similar to the consensus sequence are identified by means of a simple sequence alignment.

Imbalances in the descriptor dataset (e.g. skewness, kurtosis) can influence dramatically the ML prediction capacity (Fig. 4.2). In particular, some ML algorithms can end up ignoring the minority class entirely if it is underrepresented in the training set. It is crucial to include the minority class, on which predictions are most important. Many different techniques exist to address this issue, with random resampling being one of the most widely used. With this method, data from the majority class is randomly deleted (undersampling), and data from the minority class is duplicated (oversampling). In our case, undersampling is achieved by removing the sequences with affinities close to zero (which we assume to be noise) and many with low affinities. In turn, oversampling is achieved by duplicating sequences with high affinities, changing only one nucleotide out of the consensus sequence region.

Figure 4.2: Examples of data imbalance in the training dataset. Highly skewed affinities (left, protein family ZFP263), with many low affinity points and few high affinities. Slightly skewed affinities (right, protein family SDCCAG8), with many low affinity points but a non-negligible amount of high affinity points. The x-axis of the plots at the top represents the number of experimental samples, whereas the y-axis represents affinity (from 0 to 1). The x-axis of the histograms at the bottom represents affinity (from 0 to 1), whereas the y-axis represents frequency

Finally, representative data from all descriptors, including base pair step translational and rotational parameters and sequence-based features are joined with the experimental affinities and used to train a Random Forest Regressor. For each tetramer in the input sequence (n-mer) the descriptors are retrieved. The tetramers are defined by each 4-mer overlapping sliding windows in the input sequences. Preliminary results can be seen in Fig. 4.3.

After training the ML model, the final step is comparing the predicted affinity using these parameters with the experimental ones. The performance of the ML has been assessed using the coefficient of determination, R^2 . In general, having sequence composition and structural features is better than having just sequence composition or just structural features. It can also clearly be seen that the algorithm is robust for skewed datasets (i.e. those with few high affinity values, see Fig. 4.2), with correlations larger than 0.7 on average, and a maximal correlation of 0.92. In contrast, for less skewed datasets (e.g. SDCCAG8 protein family, see Fig. 4.2), the algorithm is unable to correctly predict experimental binding affinities, and yields correlations below 0.5.

Figure 4.3: Preliminary results for 19 protein families. Color-coded heatmap representing R^2 correlation values for predicted vs. experimental affinities. The x-axis represents three different predictors: PRESENCE, trained with just the PSPM probabilities (sequence composition), AVG+DIAG, trained with just the helical parameters values (structural features), and PRES+AVG+DIAG, trained with both values

Based on these promising results, we plan to improve the implementation of the workflow. For example, results could be improved by refining the training dataset. However, it represents well how this type of workflows work and how they can benefit from the work in the BioExcel CoE. The huge amount of data needed to extract the DNA flexibility properties can be generated using the pre-exascale workflows presented in D2.3 – First Release of Demonstration Workflows. The iterative process of identifying the best training dataset and the work to be done to balance the dataset can benefit from the use of Jupyter Notebooks. MD analyses and ML training and testing can benefit from the BioBB ML (biobb_ml, see section 2) and MD analysis (biobb_analysis) modules, offering tool interoperability and workflow reproducibility.

The overall goal of this project is to generate a BioBB workflow with all the routines presented in this deliverable. It will be exported as a Jupyter Notebook and shared with the scientific community, following the process presented in deliverable D2.3 (and to be included in D2.7 – Final Release of Demonstration Workflows).

4.2 RNA Stacking: Prediction of Quantum Interaction Energies

Despite the central dogma of biology that considered RNA a mere intermediate (DNA → RNA → Proteins) between the genetic information (DNA) and the molecular effectors of the cell (Proteins), it is now clear that RNA has a much more important role. It can effectively store the genetic material in some viruses (e.g. SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus), as well as catalyze chemical reactions (ribozymes). To date, we know that over 90% of the genome is transcribed into RNA, but only a minor part is translated into proteins, indicating that RNA might be playing crucial biological roles which are yet to be discovered.

The biological function of any molecule is a direct consequence of its atomic structure and dynamics, which determine how the molecule interacts with others. Acquiring knowledge about RNA structure can be approached from an experimental and theoretical point of view. In this project we are interested in theoretical approaches for modeling RNA [27].

RNA folding and its stability is strongly dependent on stacking interactions [28]. They can be defined as the overlap of the pi cloud of electrons of close-by nucleobases (Fig 4.4). Understanding and correctly modeling these interactions is key to advance our understanding of RNA structure and dynamics.

Figure 4.4: RNA folding and stability depends strongly on stacking interactions (shown in pink) [Image taken from: <http://origins-of-life-fg.arc.nasa.gov/>]

Modeling RNA structures is a problem that can be approached on multiple scales that range from the most fundamental physics-based to the purely knowledge-based methods. Here we refer to the first category only. Quantum Mechanics (QM) calculations represent the most precise methods for the purpose, but are the most inefficient. They treat the subatomic particles (nucleus and electrons) as separate entities and apply Schrödinger's equation for describing the electron clouds and capturing physicochemical effects as polarization. On the other hand, Classical Mechanics (CM) treat atoms as the smallest unit and their behavior is represented by a combination of bonded (Newton equations) and non-bonded (Coulomb and Van der Waals equations) forces. These equations require finely tuned parameters, also known as force fields. They represent a more time-effective alternative to QM. Force fields are used in MD to run simulations and compare them with experimental results [29]. Current RNA force fields overestimate the stability of stacking interactions [30], and this work is focused on improving these non-bonded interactions. We hypothesize that the closer the prediction is to the QM energy, the better the force field. Here is where ML comes into play.

We generated a dataset of stacked nucleobases from two origins: 1) RNA structures from the Protein Data Bank were analyzed [31] and all nucleobase pairs below a distance threshold of 5 Å were extracted, capped with a methyl group and replaced by a minimized homolog (Fig 4.5A); 2) for all combinations of nucleobase pairs (AA, AC ... UU), a conformational enrichment was applied generating conformational scans (Fig 4.5B).

Figure 4.5: Representation of the process of (A) getting stacked nucleobases from PDB structures and (B) generating scans of alternative stacked conformations

For all structures, the interaction energy was calculated at the QM level (B3LYP/Def2TZVPP EmpiricalDispersion=GD3BJ) [32] and the CM level using the parmbsc0 force field. With these values as targets, we trained different ML models based on the interatomic distances between the nucleobases as input features.

ML models are sensitive to the quantity and quality of the input features, which are distances in this case. Some interaction properties can be captured at different distance powers (e.g. electrostatics happen at the 1st power, Van der Waals (VdW) attraction at the 6th power and VdW repulsion is usually modeled at the 12th power). Therefore, different ML models were generated using different combinations of distance powers. The more powers included, the better the result, but at the cost of making the training and the prediction slower. The most cost-effective selection of powers was 1-6-12, just as in the current force fields (Fig 4.6).

Figure 4.6: Root Mean Square Error (left) and R² squared (right) for the different datasets and combinations of powers used in the ML model

After having tested multiple nonlinear regressors with automated learning packages (e.g. TPOT), the simpler multilinear regressor was chosen since the results were as good as other more complex models, with the benefit of avoiding overfitting. When comparing the results from the ML model with classical force field predictions (Fig 4.7), it becomes clear that ML methods get closer to the QM values and evidence that distances are enough for yielding good predictions. How this research will become part of atomistic simulations is an ongoing effort.

Figure 4.7: (A) QM energy vs. CM energy prediction with the parmbsc0 force field for the UU dataset. (B) Testing and training predictions by the QM-based ML model for the same dataset

QM calculations needed to generate the target (ML-dependent variable) require a significant amount of computational power. A number of independent calculations could be launched in parallel on HPC supercomputers using the PyCOMPSs workflow manager (work in progress). The generation of the dataset of stacked nucleobases from the Protein Data Bank, including conformational enrichment and nucleobases capping, and the calculation of atomistic distances on the whole dataset (ML-independent variables) were written as a Python pipeline. It can be easily ported to a reproducible BioBB workflow. The whole pipeline, including the ML model training and testing can also benefit from Jupyter Notebooks, similarly to the previous project. The goal of this project is also to generate a BioBB workflow with all the routines presented in this deliverable: it will be exported as a Jupyter Notebook and shared with the scientific community, following the process presented in the deliverable D2.3 (to be included in D2.7 – Final Release of Demonstration Workflows).

5 BioExcel-CV19 Database & Server

BioExcel's CoE reacted to the COVID-19 pandemic by redirecting efforts to different projects focusing on the viral structure and drug design. One of the most important projects, co-orchestrated with the Molecular Sciences Software Institute (MolSSI), is the [COVID-19 Molecular Structure and Therapeutics Hub](#). The site was presented as a community-driven data repository and curation service for molecular structures, models, therapeutics, and simulations related to COVID-19 computational research. The repository was designed from scratch to share data from the scientific community, making science and data completely open to better tackle the COVID-19 global emergency. The Hub has become a reference repository with huge amounts of useful information gathered in one single portal.

One of the most important data types shared by the Hub is MD simulations. Renowned groups in the field (e.g. D.E. Shaw, Riken, Folding@home) have contributed to the repository, summing up milliseconds of data. Trajectories stored include different structures involved in the process of virus infection and virus life cycle, such as the now well-know spike protein (involved in the binding to the human host cell), the human Angiotensin Converting enzyme 2 –hACE2- (to which the spike protein binds), or the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (playing a key role in the replication and transcription cycle of the virus). Some of these raw trajectories are just linked from the Hub and maintained by the authors, but others are stored in project-dedicated Amazon Web Services (AWS) storage, freely offered to the scientific community via just a simple [data intake form](#).

The COVID-19 Molecular Structure and Therapeutics Hub is today an essential repository of the field. It is a central point where to find and download useful data for research. The [BioExcel-CV19](#) database and associated web server (Fig. 5.1) expands the power of the Hub, including interactive graphical representations of the trajectories and analyses performed on them.

Figure 5.1: BioExcel-CV19 web portal

The main objective of the BioExcel-CV19 project is to generate a tool for scientists interested in the COVID-19 research to interactively and graphically check key structural and flexibility features stemming from MDs. As these features vary depending on the structure analyzed, specific analyses were performed, uploaded to the database, and represented in the web portal. These analyses and key features were collected by direct interaction with the simulations authors. As an example, trajectories corresponding to the virus Receptor Binding Domain (RBD) attached to the human Angiotensin Converting enzyme 2 (hACE2), the RBD-hACE2 complex, include interface observables (e.g. residue distances, hydrogen bonds), allowing an easy analysis of their behaviour along the simulation (Fig. 5.2).

Figure 5.2: Example of a specific analysis: RBD-hACE2 interface residue distance heatmap. By clicking on a heatmap cell, a pop-up with the representation of the specific pair of residues is shown

The set of analyses computed on the trajectories are all integrated in a single workflow with the aim of progressively exporting it to the BioBB library to make it reproducible. It is built using a combination of analysis tools from MD packages (e.g. GROMACS, VMD) and useful Python libraries for MD analysis (e.g. Pytraj, Prody). Specific tools are integrated when needed, such as the Fpocket tool to detect protein cavities and their changes in volume along the simulations.

All the analyses integrated in the web portal are completely interactive. Whenever possible, a direct link from the analysis to the 3D representation is offered, using the NGL viewer [33] (see Fig. 5.2). The fast extraction of a particular snapshot from the whole trajectory is possible thanks to the NoSQL Mongo database backend powering the server. The whole set of trajectories (atomistic 3D coordinates for every atom and every frame of the simulation) and analyses are stored in this distributed database and efficiently retrieved on the

fly from any web portal request. The MongoDB distributed database was installed and configured for the BioExcel project in the BSC premises ([Starlife Cloud Infrastructure](#)), with the future possibility to work on *Big Data* projects. The infrastructure is composed of twelve different Virtual Machines (VMs), each of them with a local 6 TB disk, configured as a combination of six shards (i.e. distributed data servers) containing two replication machines (i.e. mirroring data services) each. Database sharding offers load balancing, distributing a set of tasks over the set of available resources, and allows for parallelized data processing, ultimately making the overall processing more efficient. The current database has a total capacity of 36 TB of data (extendable to up to 300 TB), and is now storing 1.5 TB just for the BioExcel-CV19 project. The server portal is also implemented on top of a VM deployed in the same Starlife Cloud, allowing a direct connection to the database using the Node.js MongoDB driver.

The project is an example of how the combination of HPC and HPDA is now helping the scientific community. The Starlife Supercomputer offers the disk space to temporarily store the trajectories registered in the BioExcel-MolSSI COVID-19 Therapeutics Hub. It also offers the hardware resources needed to run the analyses workflows. The large amount of data coming from the atomistic trajectories and their corresponding analyses is stored in the MongoDB distributed database. The entire pipeline is now automated and new COVID-19 related trajectories are currently being processed. The set of analyses will be continuously extended, according to the suggestions of the authors of MD simulations.

6 Conclusions

HPC and HPDA are both integrative parts of the modern computational biomolecular simulation field. The large amounts of data generated by the simulations run in HPC supercomputers are routinely mined using different data analytics methods, including ML and NoSQL techniques.

The BioExcel Building Blocks library has been extended with new ML tools, which will allow generating reproducible workflows including training, testing and prediction with ML models (biobb_ml category). Jupyter Notebooks tutorial workflows will be generated using this new BioBB category in the coming months, extending the collection of demonstration workflows. Besides, workflows tackling real scientific projects are being explored and will also be ported to the BioBB library, producing reproducible, ready to be shared ML workflows.

The dislib distributed ML library is getting closer to the biomolecular simulation field. Now it is able to directly read MD trajectories, split them in chunks and distribute the work between different nodes in the MareNostrum4 supercomputer and other resources offered in the PRACE network. The addition of two widely used methods in the analysis of MD trajectories (PCA and Daura's clustering) permits performing this kind of analyses on extremely large trajectories, a task that would have been impossible with standard MD analysis packages.

The BioExcel-CV19 *Big Data* database and associated web server is already offering ~200 COVID-19 related MD simulations, and is continuously updated. The set of analyses, with specific ones depending on the type of structure being studied, is extended with suggestions from the authors of the simulations. The project aims at being an interactive and graphical extension for the [BioExcel-MolSSI COVID-19 Molecular Structure and Therapeutics Hub](#). All MD trajectories registered into this hub will be stored, analysed, and presented in the BioExcel-CV19 database and the web server, offering not only a direct 3D representation of key flexibility features, but also a programmatic REST API to atomic coordinates and analyses for all trajectories stored in the NoSQL infrastructure.

This document presents examples of projects combining HPC and HPDA methods that are being developed in the BioExcel CoE. Given the current growth trend for HPC & HPDA, the technologies used in these projects are going to be essential in subsequent studies and project plans.

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8 Appendix

Building block	Wrapped tool	Description
LinearRegression	sklearn.linear_model.LinearRegression	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the model and scaler for a linear regression.
PolynomialRegression	sklearn.linear_model.LinearRegression	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the model and scaler for a polynomial regression.
RandomForestRegressor	sklearn.ensemble.RandomForestRegressor	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the model and scaler for a random forest regressor.
RegressionPredict	In house using sklearn	Makes predictions from a given model.
DecisionTree	sklearn.model.DecisionTreeClassifier	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the model and scaler for a decision tree classification.
KNeighborsCoefficient	sklearn.linear_model.LinearRegression	Trains and tests a given dataset and calculates best K coefficient for a k-nearest neighbors classification.
KNeighborsTrain	sklearn.neighbors.KNeighborsClassifier	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the model and scaler for a k-nearest neighbors classification.
LogisticRegression	sklearn.linear_model.LogisticRegression	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the model and scaler for a logistic regression.
RandomForestClassifier	sklearn.ensemble.RandomForestClassifier	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the model and scaler for a random forest classifier.
SupportVectorMachine	sklearn.svm.SVC	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the model and scaler for a support vector machine model.
ClassificationPredict	In house using sklearn	Makes predictions from a given model.
AgglomerativeCoefficient	sklearn.cluster.AgglomerativeClustering	Clusters a given dataset and calculates the best K coefficient for an agglomerative clustering.
AgglClustering	sklearn.cluster.AgglomerativeClustering	Clusters a given dataset with the agglomerative clustering method.
DBSCANClustering	sklearn.cluster.DBSCAN	Clusters a given dataset with the DBSCAN clustering method.
KMeansCoefficient	sklearn.cluster.KMeans	Clusters a given dataset and calculates the best K coefficient for a k-means clustering.
KMeansClustering	sklearn.cluster.KMeans	Clusters a given dataset with k-means clustering method.
SpectralCoefficient	sklearn.cluster.SpectralClustering	Clusters a given dataset and calculates the best coefficient for a spectral clustering.
SpecClustering	sklearn.cluster.SpectralClustering	Clusters a given dataset with the spectral clustering method.
ClusteringPredict	In house using sklearn	Makes predictions from a given model.
CorrelationMatrix	In house	Generates a correlation matrix from a given dataset.
Dendrogram	In house	Generates a dendrogram from a given dataset.
DummyVariables	In house	Maps dummy variables from a given dataset.

Building block	Wrapped tool	Description
MapVariables	In house	Maps dummy variables from a given dataset.
PairwiseComparison	In house	Generates a pairwise comparison from a given dataset.
AutoencoderNeuralNetwork	tf.keras.layers.LSTM	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the complete model for an Autoencoder Neural Network.
ClassificationNeuralNetwork	tf.keras.Sequential	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the complete model for a Neural Network Classification.
RecurrentNeuralNetwork	tf.keras.layers.LSTM	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the complete model for a Recurrent Neural Network.
RegressionNeuralNetwork	tf.keras.Sequential	Trains and tests a given dataset and saves the complete model for a Neural Network Regression.
DecodingNeuralNetwork	In house using TensorFlow	Decodes and predicts given a dataset and a model file.
PredictNeuralNetwork	In house using TensorFlow	Calculates prediction for a NN classification given a model file.
PLSComponents	sklearn.cross_decomposition.PLSRegression	Calculates the best components number for a Partial Least Square (PLS) Regression.
PLS Regression	sklearn.cross_decomposition.PLSRegression	Gives results for a Partial Least Square (PLS) Regression.
PrincipalComponentAnalysis	sklearn.decomposition.PCA	Analyses a given dataset through Principal Component Analysis (PCA).